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THE NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE RED EDGE INDEX (NDRE) IN GRAIN YIELD AND BIOMASS ESTIMATION IN MAIZE (*Zea mays* L.)

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Abstract

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is considered one of the most important crops in the world and plays an important role in human food and animal feed. Considering the importance of maize production, as well as significant variability in productivity, biomass and early grain yield evaluation may be significantly important. Crop growth monitoring by remote and proximal sensing based on spectral information could provide promising results in its prediction. In the present study, an active multispectral proximate sensor, namely the Plant-O-Meter (POM) was used in the field trial to provide early yield and biomass estimation in maize crops. The maize crop was grown under field trial conditions with various levels of nitrogen application. This study investigated the contribution of the Normalized Difference Red Edge Index (NDRE) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) on maize grain yield and biomass estimation during the season. The canopy reflectance was measured between the 4-leaf growth stages (V4) and the end of the tasseling and silking stage (VT/R1) in maize. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was applied to determine the correlations between grain yield and biomass with the NDRE and NDVI indices throughout the growing season. Maize grain yield showed a more significant positive relationship with both indices across the V4 stage, while biomass estimation showed the highest correlation at the VT/R1 growth stages. These results imply that NDRE and NDVI indices may be suitable for early yield and biomass estimation, while their accuracy depends on the growth stage of maize.

Key words: *maize, yield, biomass, proximal sensors.*